

CONSUMER DECISION-MAKING IN SUPPLEMENTATION: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW USING THE HEALTH BELIEF MODEL

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Abstract

The growing consumer interest in preventive health and wellness products has intensified the importance of understanding the psychological and behavioural factors influencing consumer decision-making in supplementation. This study systematically reviews existing research on dietary and health supplement consumption through the lens of the Health Belief Model (HBM), with a specific focus on its relevance to consumer decision-making. The systematic review followed PRISMA guidelines. Database searches of Scopus and PubMed (2014-2024) identified 407 articles, of which 21 met the inclusion criteria and were narratively synthesized. The findings indicate that supplementation behaviour is best understood as a value-risk evaluation process, in which consumers assess perceived benefits against perceived barriers under varying levels of perceived risk and behavioural capability. Perceived benefits emerge as the most dominant driver, suggesting that consumers approach supplementation as a value-seeking behaviour rather than purely a risk-avoidance response. In contrast, perceived barriers such as cost, accessibility, and uncertainty act as key inhibitors, reinforcing cost-benefit trade-offs in decision-making. Constructs such as perceived susceptibility and severity demonstrate context-specific effects, while self-efficacy and cues to action facilitate the translation of intention into behaviour. The study conceptualizes supplementation as a multi-stage consumer decision process involving risk perception, value evaluation, and behavioural execution, and highlights the enhanced explanatory power of integrating HBM with the Theory of Planned Behavior. The findings offer important implications for marketers and identify key directions for future research in preventive health consumption.

Keywords: *Health Belief Model (HBM), Consumer Decision-Making, Supplementation Behaviour, Dietary and Health Supplements, Preventive Health Consumption, Consumer Motivation.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The growing prevalence of non-communicable diseases including cancer, diabetes mellitus, osteoporosis, and cardiovascular disorders has significantly raised public interest in maintaining

healthier lifestyles (Chung et al., 2012). As an outcome of this concern, consumers are increasingly becoming interested in preventive health solutions and wellness products which can be used to minimize health risks and improve overall well-being. Therefore, health concerns have become a significant factor of consumers' food-related decisions, given the robust link between diet and the onset or prevention of such diseases (Bogue et al., 2005; Thompson et al., 2008). As underscored by various researchers (Rajasekaran & Kalaivani, 2013), products such as dietary and health supplements, functional foods, nutraceuticals, and fortified foods are enriched with specific nutrients to provide additional health benefits beyond the basic nutrition. These products not only support mental and physical performance but also contribute to reduce long-term healthcare costs and promote an active, health-conscious way of life (Siti, 2011).

This increasing consumer health awareness has driven a notable expansion in demand for health-oriented food products, leading to the rapid increase of the global health food market (Gehlhar et al., 2009). Consequently, within the context of health-related consumer behavior, research has become crucial for development of effective marketing strategies, enabling marketers to better acknowledge and anticipate consumption patterns related to health foods (Siti, 2011). Critical understanding of the drivers of consumer choices is therefore increasingly significant for businesses operating in health and wellness domain.

Dietary supplements (DSs) are defined as products that contain dietary ingredients intended to supplement the nutritional content of the diet (US Food and Drug Administration, 2018). Their usage has increased substantially due to rising health consciousness. For example, it has been reported that 76% of adults in the United States consume dietary supplements (CRN, 2017), indicating their widespread acceptance and use. The packaged supplement market is projected to reach US\$347 million by 2026, assuming the growing interest of the average Indian in preventive healthcare persists (Sadhukhan et al., 2023). As the global market for these products continues to grow, understanding of the behavioural drivers underlying supplementation consumption decision has attracted significant scholarly attention (Dwyer et al., 2018).

The Health Belief Model (HBM) was initially developed to explain why individuals adopt preventive health behaviors, which provides a framework to understand how health-related beliefs influence behavioural decisions (Tukiran et al., 2020). Individuals' health behaviours are shaped by various psychological constructs, as explained in the HBM include: perceived susceptibility, perceived severity, perceived benefits and barriers, and self-efficacy (Carpenter, 2010). Perceived susceptibility demonstrates an individual's belief in their risk of experiencing a negative health outcome, while perceived severity pertains to the extremity they attribute to that outcome. The perceived benefits of taking preventive action are contemplated against perceived barriers, which may restrain behavioural changes. Lastly, self-efficacy associates to an individual's confidence in their ability to perform health-promoting behaviors.

Although there is increasing application of the Health Belief Model in studies evaluating the supplement consumption and other health related behaviours, the existing body of knowledge remains fragmented across various contexts, populations and methodological approaches. Various constructs of the HBM were explored in the individual studies in supplement consumption, but the research findings are dispersed and inconsistent in many ways, making it difficult to conclude comprehensively regarding the determinants of consumer behaviour in supplementation domain.

In response to this backdrop, this systematic review aims to synthesize the existing evidence on how perceptions of susceptibility, severity, benefits, barriers and self-efficacy—the major constructs as outlined in the Health Belief Model— along with other relevant psychological and contextual factors, influence the consumer behavior related to dietary and health supplement consumption. By integrating findings from diverse studies this review provides clarification on how the HBM constructs collectively explain supplementation behaviours thus offering valuable insights not only for researchers and healthcare practitioners but also for marketers seeking to design consumer-centered strategies offering a nuanced understanding of consumer motivations behind supplement consumption. Ultimately, the findings could suggest more personalized, evidence-based interventions and marketing communications that empower the informed consumer choices, consumer-centered health interventions and support informed decision-making aimed at improving preventive health practices through more effective promotion of health products.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Research Design and Review Approach

This study adopts a SLR approach to synthesize and reinterpret existing research on supplementation consumer behaviour towards supplementation through the lens of Health Belief Model with a specific focus on consumer decision-making processes. Additionally, SLRs produce "higher quality of review outcomes and evidence" than typical literature reviews, according to authors who elaborate on different kinds of literature reviews (Barat et al., 2017), specifically in the interdisciplinary domain such as preventive health consumption where the insights are dispersed across the consumer behaviour and health science research (Paul & Criado, 2020). Consequently, there are three primary benefits to the formal SLR methodology:

- 1) encompasses the findings of all research on a particular subject;
- 2) considerably lessens researcher bias; and
- 3) replicability allows the review's applicability to be confirmed (Hensel, 2020).

The "PRISMA" or "Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses" reporting criteria were applied in this study (Page et al., 2020).

2.2 Information Sources and Search-Strategy

A comprehensive search of the literature was carried out utilizing the Scopus and PubMed databases, which were selected due to their extensive coverage of multidisciplinary research in consumer behaviour, health behaviour, and nutrition studies. Specifically, PubMed was chosen for access to health-related behavioural studies and Scopus for broad coverage of social science and marketing research. Studies published between 2014 to 2024 were included at the time of the database's final search. The search strategy includes entering ("title, abstract, and keywords") in the search bar: "health belief model", "supplements", "health food", "dietary supplement", "health supplement". Boolean operators (AND and OR) were used to combine the keywords for identification of studies evaluating the relationship between the Health Belief Model and supplementation related consumer behaviour. 407 records resulted in the initial search, out of which 355 were from Scopus and 52 from PubMed.

The search strategy was developed iteratively and structured around three major domains:

- a) Theoretical Framework: Health Belief Model
- b) Product Category: Dietary supplement, Health supplement and Functional food
- c) Behavioural Outcomes: Consumer behaviour, Risk perception and Behavioural intention

2.3 Eligibility Criteria

The included studies met the following requirements: they evaluated the effects of supplementation, were published in English, had a research design that was either observed or experimental, and were available in full text. Only abstracts, conference abstracts, editor's letters, brief communications, and meta-analyses, on the other hand, were not included. Furthermore, studies released prior to 2014 were not included because the different aspects of supplementation-related behavior are dynamic and constantly changing. As a result, the time-based inclusion criteria made it possible to gather the most up-to-date and pertinent data on dietary supplement and/or health supplement consumption patterns.

2.4 Study Selection and Data Extraction Process

Studies from around the globe that examined health behaviors related to supplements were included in the selection process. According to authors (Hensel, 2020) and (Page et al., 2021), the phase of screenings comprised taking two steps: Step 1- Screening of titles and abstracts to eliminate irrelevant studies, and Step 2 Screening of full texts based on predefined eligibility criteria.

E.S and S.G, two researchers screened the studies independently to ensure consistency and to reduce selection bias. Through clear discussion, the discrepancies between the researchers were resolved. S.C, the third researcher, assessed the studies with uncertainty and meeting the inclusion criteria partially to ensure appropriateness of the final selection. This multi reviewer concept enhances methodological rigor and objectivity, an important criterion for high quality systematic reviews (Booth et al., 2021). Following the process of screening, 21 studies were included in the final review of the study. Figure 1, illustrates the selection process in the PRISMA flow diagram.

2.5 Data Extraction and Coding Framework

We employed a structured data extraction protocol to systematically capture relevant information from the included studies. The study incorporated a Theory driven coding framework, in alignment with the study's conceptual orientation towards consumer decision-making. The extracted categories are following:

- A) Study Characteristics (authors, year, geographical context and sample size)
- B) Research design and method of analysis
- C) Operationalization of HBM constructs (perceived barriers, perceived benefits, perceived susceptibility, perceived severity, self-efficacy, cues to action).
- D) Behavioural outcomes
- E) Contextual and moderating variables

This process of structured coding enabled transforming individual study into analytical themes, which facilitated the cross-sectional differentiation and supported the identification of value-risk evaluation patterns, which are discussed in the result section.

2.6 Assessment of the Study Quality

In our research paper, the risk of bias for the qualified studies was evaluated using a modified version of the Newcastle-Ottawa scale for cross-sectional studies (Herzog et al., 2013). Each article was assessed and assigned a score, and the overall quality was graded as "High risk of bias (0-3), Moderate risk of bias (4-6) and Low risk of bias (7-9)" (Carra et al., 2025). In our Study, confounder control in the included studies was examined using the Newcastle-Ottawa Scale to determine whether each study appropriately identified and adjusted for key covariates (Wells et al., 2014). Additionally, authors have performed the citation analysis which is represented in the figure number 2. Table 1 represents the Assessment of Study Quality.

2.7 Data Synthesis

The lack of homogeneity in the interventions and results was one of the many factors that prevented meta-analysis. Because of this, this comprehensive analysis employs a descriptive, which permits the incorporation of various study designs comprising both qualitative and quantitative without requiring statistical pooling to have homogeneous data. This allows for a thorough investigation of how the Health Belief Model is applied to consumers' supplement consumption behavior.

Table 1: Assessment of Study Quality

Study	Sample Size	Exposure/ Outcome Ascertainment	Confounder Control	Selection (Max 5)	Compatibility (Max 2)	Outcome (Max 3)	NOS Score (0-10)	Risk of Bias	Study Quality
Mahmudiono et al., 2022	140	Valid measures (pre-post)	Limited	3	1	2	6	Moderate	Moderate
Caballero-Apaza et al., 2022	192	Validated scale	Limited	4	1	3	8	Low	High
Natarajan et al., 2024	444	Self-report survey	Partial	3	2	3	8	Low	High
Kurniawan et al., 2022	225	Pre-post measures	Moderate	4	1	3	8	Low	High
Febian & Annuar, 2021	250	Standardized survey	Partial	3	1	3	7	Moderate	Moderate
Costa & Suzane, 2020	NR	Qualitative (FGD)	Not applicable	2	0	2	4	High	Low
Febian et al., 2021	250	Validated constructs	Partial	3	2	3	8	Low	High
Gamboa et al., 2020	766	Self-report survey	Moderate	3	2	3	8	Low	High
Lee et al., 2020	550	Validated scales	Moderate	4	2	3	9	Low	High
Shiraishi et al., 2021	194	Objective intake measures	Moderate	4	1	3	8	Low	High
Tzeng et al., 2022	803	Self-report survey	Partial	3	2	3	8	Low	High
Natarajan & Jayapal, 2022	445	Standardized survey	Partial	3	2	3	8	Low	High
Teng et al., 2020	1000	Self-report survey	Partial	3	2	3	8	Low	High
Rezai et al., 2017	2004	National survey	Moderate	4	2	3	9	Low	High
Araban et al., 2017	76	Validated questionnaire	Moderate	3	1	3	7	Moderate	Moderate
Jalili et al., 2019	333	HBM-based tool	Partial	3	1	3	7	Moderate	Moderate
DelGiudice et al., 2018	92	Self-report	Limited	2	1	2	5	Moderate	Moderate
Nechitilo et al., 2016	63	Qualitative interviews	Not applicable	2	0	2	4	High	Low
Pan et al., 2019	1075	Survey (HBM-based)	Partial	3	1	3	7	Moderate	Moderate
Wang & Li, 2015	384	Standardized survey	Partial	3	2	3	8	Low	High
Espeño et al., 2024	250	Self-report survey	Partial	3	2	3	8	Low	High

Figure 1: The PRISMA flow diagram representing the course of particulars through the distinct stages of the systematic review

3. RESULTS

355 papers were found in the first searches on Scopus and 52 from PubMed. 21 articles made it into the narrative synthesis after the duplicates were eliminated and the inclusion/exclusion criteria were applied [Figure 1].

Table 1 furnishes a brief summary of the studies comprehended.

Table 1: Brief summary of the studies

Authors	Aim of the Study	Study Methods	Sample and Analysis	Main Results/ Findings
Mahmudiono et al., 2022	To evaluate whether an HBM-based nutritional awareness program changes attitudes toward supplement and nutrient consumption among individuals with and	Quantitative	Sample size 140 and Inferential analysis using paired-sample t-tests (pre-post within groups) and independent-samples t-tests (between-group	Nutrition education and socialization initiatives positively reinforce supplement and mineral consumption for COVID-19 prevention.

	without prior COVID-19 infection.		differences in perceived severity and susceptibility).	
Caballero-Apaza et al., 2022	To develop and validate a scale measuring perception influencing adherence to iron supplementation among mothers of anaemic children in a high-altitude Peruvian region.	Quantitative	Cross-sectional study of 192 mothers of anaemic children in a high-altitude Peruvian region; HBM-based scale development and validation.	The HBM-based scale effectively validated perceptions influencing adherence to iron supplementation among mothers of anaemic children.
Natarajan et al., 2024	To examine post-COVID-19 consumption of branded functional beverages and assess the moderating role of subjective norms using integrated behavior change models.	Quantitative	Convenience sample of 537 Indian adults (444 valid responses); analyzed using PLS-SEM based on an integrated VAB-HBM-TPB model.	Media-driven COVID-19 awareness increases interest in healthy nutriments, which mediates purchase intention for functional beverages; subjective norms significantly moderate these relationships.
Kurniawan et al., 2022	To assess the impact of HBM-based self-medication learning media on health students' supplement-related behavior.	Quantitative	Quasi-experimental (pre-post control group) study with 225 participants selected via stratified random sampling; analyzed using paired-sample t-tests.	HBM-based self-medication educational media improves students' attitudes and is scalable across technological and geographic contexts.
Febian & Annuar, 2021	To examine the relationship between perceived barriers, perceived susceptibility, and older consumers' intention to purchase functional nutriments.	Quantitative	Survey of Malaysian older adults (n = 250 valid responses); analyzed using PLS-SEM.	Perceived barriers and cues to action significantly influence older consumers' intention to consume functional foods, while perceived susceptibility is not significant.
Costa & Suzane, 2020	To examine how integrated HBM-TPB explains functional meal choice and how consumers evaluate nutrition and health claims.	Qualitative	Focus group discussions guided by TPB-HBM-based semi-structured questions; analyzed using qualitative content analysis.	Proposes an integrated HBM-TPB-TRA framework offering a structured and practically applicable model for understanding consumer behavior.
Febian et al., 2021	To analyze consumers' intention to purchase functional nutriments using HBM antecedents.	Quantitative	250 valid surveys (83% response rate); analyzed using SEM for measurement and structural model testing (direct effects and construct validity).	Perceived benefits and barriers directly influence healthy eating decisions, while perceived susceptibility and cues to action do not significantly affect functional food intention.
Gamboa et al., 2020	To assess the effect of HBM-based interpersonal communication on pregnant women's knowledge, attitudes, and intentions toward	Quantitative	Cross-sectional survey of 766 pregnant women (TPB-HBM); analyzed using logistic and modified linear regression comparing IPC vs. non-IPC groups.	Low-intensity interventions improve knowledge but not behavior; effective change requires greater exposure, reduced barriers, and enhanced perceived susceptibility and self-efficacy.

	IFA supplementation and iron-rich food consumption.			
Lee et al., 2020	To examine consumers' repurchase behavior of gastrointestinal health supplements using HBM and perceived behavioral control (PBC).	Quantitative	550 valid questionnaires (80.6% response rate); analyzed using SPSS with Cronbach's α , CFA, and SEM for reliability, validity, and structural relationships.	PBC, perceived benefits, severity, and susceptibility positively influence repurchase intention, while perceived barriers negatively affect it; intention, in turn, drives repurchase behavior.
Shiraishi et al., 2021	To evaluate the impact of HBM-based postpartum dietary interventions on nutrient intake and food consumption at six months.	Quantitative	Randomized postpartum study (intervention n = 100; control n = 94); analyzed using Mann-Whitney U test for between-group dietary intake differences.	HBM-based dietary intervention modestly improves postpartum intake of key nutrients, indicating potential for enhancing maternal nutrition.
Tzeng et al., 2022	To examine the mediating role of product knowledge and the moderating effects of trust and distrust within the HBM framework.	Quantitative	Online survey with 803 respondents; hypotheses tested using structural equation modeling (SEM).	Perceived susceptibility is a stronger predictor of supplement attitudes than severity; product knowledge mediates the relationship between susceptibility and product attitude.
Natarajan & Jayapal, 2022	To examine post-pandemic consumption behavior of branded functional beverages using an integrated TPB-HBM framework.	Quantitative	Survey of adult branded functional beverage consumers (n = 445 valid responses); analyzed using PLS-SEM.	Integrated TPB-HBM explains post-pandemic functional beverage consumption, highlighting the need for policy-driven promotion of healthier, resilient food systems.
Teng et al., 2020	To examine determinants of Malaysian consumers' intention to use superfoods using an updated integrated HBM framework.	Quantitative	Purposive sample of 1,000 participants; analyzed using structural equation modeling (SEM).	HBM constructs (susceptibility, severity, benefits, barriers) are validated as key determinants of consumers' supplement consumption intentions.
Rezai et al., 2017	To assess Malaysian consumers' intention to purchase natural functional foods using HBM antecedents.	Quantitative	Nationwide survey of 2,004 households; analyzed using SEM and descriptive statistics.	Attitude partially mediates the effects of perceived benefits, barriers, and susceptibility on purchase intention, but does not mediate subjective norms.
Araban et al., 2017	To evaluate the effect of HBM-based nutrition education on pregnant women's intake of calories, iron, and folic acid supplements.	Quantitative	Quasi-experimental study of 76 pregnant women from four urban health centers; HBM-based questionnaire; analyzed using Chi-square, t-test, Mann-	HBM-based educational interventions improve pregnant women's iron and folic acid intake, with significant public health implications for anaemia prevention.

			Whitney U, and Wilcoxon tests (SPSS).	
Jalili et al., 2019	To identify factors influencing omega-3 supplement use for Alzheimer's disease prevention among the elderly using HBM.	Quantitative	Analytical cross-sectional study of 333 elderly in Tehran (stratified random sampling); HBM-based questionnaire; analyzed using SPSS.	Omega-3 supplement use for AD prevention is significantly associated with knowledge and HBM constructs, supporting targeted educational interventions for the elderly.
DelGiudice et al., 2018	To examine whether HBM dimensions are associated with primary care physicians' prescribing of vitamin D (600–1,000 IU) to children aged 1–18.	Quantitative	Descriptive correlational study of 92 primary care paediatric clinicians from 14 independent practices (selective sampling).	Primary care paediatricians demonstrate strong awareness of vitamin D deficiency and its risk factors in children aged 1–18.
Nechitilo et al., 2016	To identify factors influencing initiation and adherence to supplementation among women in the PRECONCEPT randomized controlled trial.	Qualitative	Mixed qualitative study with 39 in-depth interviews and 4 focus groups (24 VHWs); HBM-guided thematic analysis of adherence and initiation factors.	Perceived susceptibility and severity drive initiation of supplement use, while perceived benefits and barriers determine long-term adherence.
Pan et al., 2019	To examine how perceived benefits, barriers, and risk of visual impairment influence dietary supplement use using the HBM.	Qualitative	Survey of 1,075 Taiwanese pharmacy patrons using an HBM-based questionnaire developed via focus groups.	Perceived benefits exert a stronger influence on supplement use than perceived risk, underscoring the need for greater awareness of visual impairment risks.
Wang & Li, 2015	To extend the HBM by incorporating environmental cues and personal stress into the model.	Quantitative	In-person survey of 384 Taiwanese health food consumers; analyzed using structural equation modeling (SEM).	Incorporating environmental cues and perceived stress into HBM enhances understanding of health food consumption behavior.
Espeño et al., 2024	To examine determinants of fitness supplement intake among enthusiasts using an integrated TPB–HBM–TEMPA framework.	Quantitative	Purposive sample of 250 respondents; analyzed using SEM (SmartPLS 3.0) to examine determinants of actual consumption.	The study's findings presented both the immediate and secondary impacts of different variables, and their approach was deemed useful for producing campaigns to raise awareness about the importance of nutritional supplements and, thereby assisting users in selecting the appropriate supplements for consumption.

In terms of geographical context, this review maps the distribution of studies applying the Health Belief Model (HBM) to supplementation behavior across diverse national settings. The existing literature predominantly focuses on countries in Asia and Latin America, with a notable concentration of research conducted in **Indonesia** (Mahmudiono et al., 2022; Kurniawan et al., 2022; Gamboa et al., 2020), **Peru** (Caballero-Apaza et al., 2022), **India** (Natarajan et al., 2024, 2022),

Malaysia (Febian et al., 2021; Teng et al., 2020; Rezai et al., 2017), and **Taiwan** (Lee et al., 2020; Pan et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2015). Additional contributions were identified from **Brazil** (Costa et al., 2020), **Japan** (Shiraishi et al., 2021), **China** (Tzeng et al., 2022), **Iran**—including **Khuzestan** (Araban et al., 2017) and **Tehran** (Jalili et al., 2019)—as well as the **United States** (DelGiudice et al., 2018). This geographic diversity underscores the global applicability of the HBM framework in understanding supplement use behaviors while also reflecting regional variations in health priorities and intervention strategies.

As illustrated in Figure 2, the included studies were published between 2015 and 2024, reflecting a growing scholarly interest in applying HBM to supplement and functional food consumption over the past decade. Across this literature set, the main objective was to identify which HBM antecedents (e.g., perceived benefits, barriers, severity, and cues to action) most significantly influenced behavioral intention and actual supplement use. This trend underscores the enduring utility of HBM in understanding health-related decision-making across diverse populations and contexts.

Figure 2: Represents the number of citations of the selected articles Year-wise

The final synthesis included 21 studies, following the screening process guided by PRISMA. The analysis indicates that there are consistent, but context-specific, patterns on how the core constructs of the Health Belief Model (HBM) impact the consumer decision-making in supplementation. Instead of acting independently, as these constructs interact to influence the perception of value, risk, and behavioural capability, which together create supplement adoption and continuity.

3.1 Perceived Severity

Validated by 7 studies (Caballero-Apaza et al., 2022; Tzeng et al., 2022; Shiraishi et al., 2021; Teng et al., 2020; Lee et al., 2020; Araban et al., 2017; Nechitilo et al., 2016), perceived severity was found to be relevant particularly in clinical and high-risk contexts including anaemia, maternal health, and nutritional deficiencies. However, according to Tzeng et al., 2022, severity may not be an effective

force to act upon unless accompanied by a feeling of vulnerability or overt behavioural indications. It indicates that severity is a factor in perception of risk but it does not solely define the decision outcomes.

3.2 Perceived Susceptibility

Out of 11 studies, which estimated perceived susceptibility, 7 studies reported perceived susceptibility as significant predictor (Tzeng et al., 2022; Mahmudiono et al., 2022; Febian et al., 2021; Febian et al., 2021; Jalili et al., 2019; Rezai et al., 2017; Nechitilo et al., 2016). The effect of the construct was greater with high risk groups like the aged populations and postpartum women. Nevertheless, the studies by Febian et al., 2022 and Rezai et al., 2021 did not indicate that susceptibility made any significant difference among the general population, meaning that this construct can be context-specific and probably more applicable when combined with perceived severity.

3.3 Perceived Benefit

Perceived benefit was the most consistently supported predictor of consumption behavior, reported as significant in 15 out of 21 studies (Kurniawan et al., 2022; Natarajan et al., 2022; Febian et al., 2021; Shiraishi et al., 2021; Gamboa et al., 2020; Lee et al., 2020; Costa et al., 2020; Teng et al., 2020; Jalili et al., 2019; Pan et al., 2019; DelGiudice et al., 2018; Rezai et al., 2017; Araban et al., 2017; Nechitilo et al., 2016; Wang et al., 2015). In all the reporting studies, consumers had a higher likelihood of adopting supplements after having a perceived clearly and personally relevant health benefits, which included prevention of diseases, boosted immunity and well-being. This implies that the formation of perceived value is a dominant cause of supplementation behaviour in which the consumer considers the products in terms of their perceived functional effects and not in terms of abstract health information.

3.4 Perceived Barriers

10 studies identified perceived barriers as a critical constraint to supplement consumption, specifically among older adults, pregnant women, and low-income groups (e.g., Febian et al., 2021; Febian et al., 2021; Teng et al., 2020; Lee et al., 2020; Gamboa et al., 2020; Pan et al., 2019; Rezai et al., 2017; Araban et al., 2017; Nechitilo et al., 2016; Wang et al., 2015;). These results suggest that a cost-benefit assessment process is done when it comes to supplementation choices, perceived barriers could slow down the adoption of a supplement by the consumer despite the benefits being appreciated. This can be especially seen in vulnerable consumer groups, with constraints being a more dominant influence on behaviour.

3.5 Cues to Action

7 out of 8 studies confirmed the significant effect of cues to action in motivating health behavior (e.g., Mahmudiono et al., 2022; Kurniawan et al., 2022; Febian et al., 2021; **Gamboa et al., 2020**; Teng et al., 2020; **Araban et al., 2017**; **Nechitilo et al., 2016**). These cues ranged from media campaigns and public health advisories to interpersonal counselling and structured education programs. Notably, Gamboa et al., 2020 and Araban et al., 2017 found interpersonal or high-intensity cues to be more effective than general or passive ones.

3.6 Self-Efficacy and Perceived Behavioral Control

Self-efficacy and perceived behavioural control were integrated into several extended-HBM frameworks. 5 studies confirmed (Natarajan et al., 2022; Costa et al., 2020; Lee et al., 2020; Gamboa et al., 2020; Jalili et al., 2019) that these constructs significantly impacted both purchase intention and consumption behavior. The finding indicates that that supplementation is more likely to be adopted when consumers feel competent, educated, and feel that they can make decisions that are related to health. This underscores the influence of behavioural capability, in which knowledge and confidence allows the intention to be transferred into actual consumption behaviour.

3.7 Hybrid Model Integration

5 studies (Natarajan et al., 2024; Espeño et al., 2024; Costa et al., 2020; Gamboa et al., 2020; Lee et al., 2020) adopted integrated frameworks combining HBM with the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) or Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA). These hybrid models enhanced explanatory power by incorporating social influence, behavioural intention and perceived control. This indicates that the individual health beliefs cannot be considered alone in determining the supplementation behaviour and that the social and motivational factors also play a role in the understanding of the consumer decision making.

3.8 Population Diversity and Intervention Insights

The reviewed studies covered diverse populations across various regions, enhancing the generalisability of the findings. 6 intervention-based studies (Mahmudiono et al., 2022; Kurniawan et al., 2022; Shiraishi et al., 2021; Gamboa et al., 2020; Araban et al., 2017; Nechitilo et al., 2016) demonstrated that HBM-based education significantly improved both intention and actual consumption behavior. However, low-intensity interventions or minimal information had limited impact, emphasizing the need for personalized and context-rich cues.

4. DISCUSSION

Within the context of consumer behaviour, this systematic review indicates that the decision to adopt supplementation ought to be viewed not as a health-related response, but as a cognitive appraisal decision, which is based on value - risk trade-offs. Though the theoretical background of the Health Belief Model (HBM) offers a practical theoretical basis, the evidence suggests that the constructs of the model do not act independently, but as components of an overall decision-making process where consumers evaluate the perceived benefits against the perceived barriers at different levels of perceived risk and behavioural competence (Mitchell, 1999).

A key insight emerging from the synthesis is that perceived benefits are the central driver of supplementation behaviour. In the studies reviewed, consumers were found to be more inclined to adopt and persevere in adopting the supplements when they had the ability to relate them with tangible and personally relevant outcomes, like increased immunity, prevention of diseases, or better health. This finding indicates that contemporary consumers research, which is directed towards the notion that health-related consumption act as a value-driven decision-making process, where consumers assess the functional and long-term benefits prior to adoption (Kushwah et al., 2019; Rana & Paul, 2020). Hence, supplementation behaviour can be better acknowledged as value-seeking rather than mostly risk avoidant consumption.

This paper contributes to the literature of consumer behaviour in three ways. First, it redefines the Health Belief Model in a consumer decision making model and proves that supplementation behaviour is value-based in its motivation and not necessarily health-based motivation. Second, it recognizes perceived benefits as a leading force of consumer behaviour that will emphasize the importance of perceived value in preventive health consumption. Third, it contributes to the literature by enabling the incorporation of HBM with other complementary theories like Theory of Planned Behavior hence providing a more detailed explanation of consumer decision-making that considers cognitive, social and behavioural aspects (Ajzen, 1991).

The perceived barriers on the other hand serve as important inhibitors which helps to strengthen the idea that supplementation decisions are based on the cost-benefits evaluation process. Factors like price, access, lack of trust and worries about side effects can neutralize the appeal of perceived benefits. The findings underscore that the effects of barriers seem to be more significant in the case of vulnerable consumer groups, such as older segments and low-income individuals, which implies that resource limitations and perceived risk increase the prominence of barriers. This aligns with broader findings in health consumption research, where perceived constraints significantly moderate behavioural adoption despite awareness of benefits (Rana & Paul, 2020).

The perceived susceptibility and perceived severity roles are seen to be more contextual and relatively weaker in consumer decision making. Although these constructs are theoretically core in the HBM, the results indicate that they have weak predictive ability in most situations of general consumption and become more relevant in high-risk groups. Consumer behaviour perspective might be explained by low urgency and abstractness of health risks, which will diminish their effect on decision-making. This observation is supported by research on health risk perception, which suggests that risk awareness alone is often insufficient to drive behavioural change unless accompanied by perceived value and actionable efficacy (Brewer et al., 2007). This leads to the perception that supplementation is not as much of risk avoidance behaviour, but rather as optional enhancement behaviour as it relates to perceived value.

The other significant observation is connected with the use of the cues to action that could be re-conceptualised as the external stimuli or marketing triggers within the context of consumer behaviour. The results suggest that consumer behaviour in relation to the recommendations of the healthcare professionals, interpersonal communication, and specific educational interventions are highly susceptible to cues, which are personalized and high in credibility. This implies that successful consumer involvement in the supplementation market is not only pegged on information sharing, but also strategy in use of sources of trust and persuasive communication mediums that increase awareness and perceived relevance (Champion & Skinner, 2008).

In addition, the incorporation of self-efficacy and perceived behavioural control also bring out the significance of consumer capability and confidence in terms of the intention to action. Supplementation behaviours are more apt to be adopted by consumers who believe that they are knowledgeable, competent and able to make informed decision. This further emphasizes the fact that it is not only motivation that drives behavioural execution, but perceived ability, which further underlines the relevance of consumer education and empowerment in the influence of health-related consumption (Gamboa et al., 2020).

An important theoretical contribution of this review, is the fact that the explanatory value of the HBM can be potentially maximised by integrating with the other complementary behavioural theories, specifically, the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) and Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA). Subjective norms and the perceived behavioural control are introduced as constructs, which makes it possible to realize a more comprehensive understanding of consumer decision-making including the mechanisms of social influence, intention formation, and behavioural execution. According to this combined approach, supplementation behaviour can be modulated not just by personal health beliefs but also by social context and motivational conditions which provides a more integrated approach to consumer study.

The integrated finding suggests a conceptualization of supplementation behaviour as a multi-stage consumer decision process, that is, perception of risk, value appraisal and behavioural implementation. In this process, the main benchmark of evaluation is perceived benefits and barriers whereas susceptibility and severity form the evaluation context and self-efficacy and cues are the means of inducing the transition between intention and actual behaviour. This integrated perspective goes a step further in developing a deeper insight into supplementation behaviour as compared to other models of health in the sense that it entrenches it in a consumer decision model.

These insights have various meaningful implications to the marketers and other practitioners in the health and wellness industry regarding the managerial perspective of the same. Strategically, marketers ought to use value-framing strategies that focus on functional and outcome-based advantages and not on abstract health claims. Besides, perceived barriers can be minimized by pricing mechanisms, explicit labelling, and trust building mechanisms, which may dramatically improve adoption. Consumer trust and persuasion of choices can be enhanced further by the utilization of credible cues, like the recommendations of medical workers and evidence-based certifications.

5. RESEARCH GAP

This review identifies gaps in the present literature. First, although perceived susceptibility and severity were included in multiple studies, their inconsistent impact calls for context-specific or population-segmented investigations. Second, longitudinal and experimental studies remain limited, making it difficult to draw conclusions about causality. Third, while self-efficacy and behavioural control emerged as significant constructs, they are still underutilized in several HBM-based models and finally, few studies explored the impact of sociocultural and environmental cues, which are increasingly significant in digital health contexts.

6. CONCLUSION

This systematic literature review synthesizes the major findings from 21 studies to comprehensively assess the application of the Health Belief Model (HBM) in explaining consumer decision-making related to dietary and health supplement consumption. The results support the importance of HBM as a robust theoretical framework for explaining consumer motivations and behavioural consequences on the basis of health-related beliefs in the context of preventive health consumption. The perceived benefits were the most consistent and impactful construct of the HBM that influenced the supplementation behaviour because the consumers are better placed to adopt and maintain supplementation when they are able to relate it to tangible health effects such as

disease prevention, immunity and well-being. Conversely, perceived barriers such as cost, access and fear of adverse effects were reported to be a major limitation especially in highly vulnerable consumer groups. These results indicate the key position of value perception and risk assessment in influencing consumer decision-making in the supplementation market.

Perceived susceptibility and perceived severity effects were more context-specific, and were more significant in the case of high-risk or health-conscious groups. This implies that consumers do not respond uniformly to health risk information but vary depending on individual traits and the circumstances. Moreover, the presence of cues to action and self-efficacy is instrumental in the conversion of intention to actual behaviour, thus the importance of specific communication, education and the confidence-building mechanisms in establishing consumer preferences should be placed.

An important theoretical input of the review is that the explanatory strength of HBM can be improved when it is integrated with the other complementary theories like the Theory of Planned Behaviour. These integrated frameworks give a more realistic explanation of consumer decision-making, and they consider the cognitive, motivational and social influences thus, expanding the applicability of HBM in consumer research.

From managerial perspective, the findings provide valuable implications to the marketers in health and wellness industry. Strategies that focus on effective and authentic communication of the benefits of the products and at the same time lower perceived impediments by making the products affordable, accessible and transparent, will most likely succeed in enhancing consumer adoption. Moreover, the use of authoritative sources, including medical practitioners, web resources, and individual communication can be viewed as the effective prompts to action and increase consumer trust in the use of supplements.

Overall, the present study contributes to the literature on the consumer research as it offers a consolidated and theory-based insight into the supplementation behaviour. The findings integrate consumer and marketing perspectives into health behaviour theory by allowing the development of more effective consumer-centred marketing policies and public health interventions in the growing supplement market.

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